

Surface Acidity, Acid Strength Distribution and Catalytic Activity of some Binary Metal Oxides Based on Alumina

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Surface acidity and acid strength distribution on the surface of metal oxides based on alumina has been measured. It is observed that the acidities and acid strengths decrease in the following order :

$\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3\text{-MoO}_3$ has on its surface an acid strength equivalent to $H_0 = -5.6$, where as other mixed oxides have on their surfaces an acid strength equivalent as follows, $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3\text{-WO}_3$ and $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3\text{-V}_2\text{O}_5$ have $H_0 = -3.0$, $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3\text{-MgO}$ and $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3\text{-BeO}$ have $H_0 = +3.3$ and $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3\text{-ThO}_2$ has $H_0 = +4.8$.

A study of the depolymerisation of paraldehyde by these catalysts indicates that only those catalysts having an acid strength equivalent to $H_0 = -3.0$ are able to catalyse the depolymerisation of paraldehyde.

ACIDIC properties of some binary metal oxide catalysts have been studied and correlated with the catalytic activities for some of the acid catalysed reactions.¹⁻³ In the present work we have attempted to measure the acidity and acid strength of some binary metal oxides based on alumina by the *n*-butylamine titration method using various indicators of $pK_a = +6.8$ to -5.6 . In order to test how the catalytic activity correlates with the acid strength of the catalyst, the depolymerisation of paraldehyde by these catalysts has been studied.

Experimental

Paraldehyde and pure quality benzene were dried over sodium, distilled and used in this investigation. All other chemicals used were AnalaR quality reagents. The indicators were synthesised by known methods and used in this work.

Preparation of catalysts :

The binary metal oxides were prepared from AnalaR quality chemicals by the precipitation and impregnation technique⁴. The mixtures of the precipitated hydroxides or the impregnated oxides were digested for several hours and then filtered, washed and dried at 120° for 20 hr. The samples thus obtained were powdered and only such samples as were collected between 100 and 150 mesh sieves were used. The powders thus obtained were subjected to heat treatment to the required temperatures for 6 hr in an electric furnace with temperature control arrangements. The samples after heat treatment were cooled in a desiccator and preserved in covered glass tubes, under vacuum.

Measurement of surface acidity :

The method that has been used to study the acidity was to titrate the surface of the catalyst with weak

bases in non-aqueous media with adsorption of the indicators on the surface. The acid strength of the surface was measured by Walling's⁵ method by observing the colour change of the base indicators with different pK_a values.

The quantitative measurement of the acidity was made by the amine titration method developed by Johnson.⁶ For this purpose, 1 g of the mixed oxide suspended in benzene was titrated with a solution of 0.1N *n*-butylamine in benzene, using neutral red ($pK_a = +6.8$), methyl red ($pK_a = +4.8$), *p*-dimethylamino azobenzene ($pK_a = +3.3$), dicinnamal acetone ($pK_a = -3.0$) and benzal acetophenone ($pK_a = -5.6$) as indicators.

Measurement of surface area :

The surface area of heat treated samples of different solid acids were measured by ethylene glycol monoethyl ether technique of Heilman and Carter.⁷

Kinetic studies :

The depolymerisation of paraldehyde reaction was selected for the study of the catalytic activity of the catalysts. For this purpose 50 ml of paraldehyde in benzene (0.05M) was pipetted out into a 100 ml quickfit flask and 1 g. of the catalyst was added. The contents of the flask were maintained at a temperature of $10^\circ \pm 0.01^\circ$ and were stirred uniformly. At regular intervals of time, the amount of acetaldehyde formed was determined volumetrically by the bisulphite method.⁸

Results and Discussion

In Table 1 are presented the values of acidity at various acid strengths of alumina based binary metal oxides. In Fig. 1, are shown the acid strength distribution of these catalysts. In this figure, the acidities in m.moles/g are plotted against the pK_a

TABLE 1. SURFACE ACIDITY AND ACID STRENGTH DISTRIBUTION OF ALUMINA BASED BINARY OXIDES

Binary oxide catalysts	Temp. of heat treatment °C	Surface area m ² /g	Acidity, m.moles/g at different pKa values					Depolymerisation of paraldehyde Rate constant K × 10 ³ min ⁻¹ g ⁻¹
			+6.8	+4.8	+3.3	-3.0	-5.6	
74% Al ₂ O ₃ -26% MoO ₃	450	82.22	0.76	0.65	0.58	0.45	0.14	34.86
84% Al ₂ O ₃ -16% WO ₃	400	83.18	0.72	0.64	0.52	0.40	n.d.	24.08
83% Al ₂ O ₃ -17% V ₂ O ₅	450	74.13	0.68	0.60	0.48	0.34	n.d.	16.28
70% Al ₂ O ₃ -30% MgO	500	93.33	0.58	0.40	0.36	—	—	No reaction
75% Al ₂ O ₃ -26% BeO	450	99.08	0.52	0.38	0.30	—	—	-do-
83% Al ₂ O ₃ -17% ThO ₂	400	46.77	0.48	0.28	—	—	—	-do-

n.d. = not detectable.

value of indicator (i.e., in terms of the H_0 values which are equal to or less than the pKa values). These plots are similar to those obtained by Tanabe *et al.*⁹ for nickel sulphate heat treated at different

Fig. 1. Acidity and acid strength distribution of binary metal oxides based on alumina.

temperatures. The acid strength of the surface increases as H_0 value decreases.

It is observed from Table 1 (Fig. 1) that the strong acid sites with an acid strength of $pK_a \leq -5.6$ appear on the surface of Al₂O₃-MoO₃. In case of Al₂O₃-WO₃ and Al₂O₃-V₂O₅, the acidities and acid strengths at $pK_a = -5.6$ could not be detected as the colour of these oxides interfered with the colour of indicator but the acidities and acid strengths at $pK_a \leq -3.0$ definitely appear on the surface of these catalysts. Al₂O₃-MgO and Al₂O₃-BeO have medium acid strength with $pK_a \leq +3.3$ and Al₂O₃-ThO₂ has weaker acidity with $pK_a \leq +4.8$. The acidities and acid strengths of metal oxides supported on Al₂O₃ decrease in the following order :

In order to test the catalytic activity of these mixed oxides, an attempt has been made to study the depolymerisation of paraldehyde in benzene solution in presence of these catalysts. The values of the first order rate constants are given in the last column of Table 1. A reference to the rate constant

values indicates that there exists a correlation between acidity at $pK_a \leq -3.0$ and catalytic activity. In case of Al₂O₃-MoO₃, Al₂O₃-WO₃ and Al₂O₃-V₂O₅ catalysts, it is seen that they have acid strength of $pK_a \leq -3.0$; hence these are catalytically active for depolymerisation of paraldehyde. Alumina based MgO, BeO and ThO₂ mixed oxides have no strong acid sites at $pK_a \leq -3.0$ but have number of sites having an acid strength of $pK_a \leq +3.3$. Therefore, those relatively weak acid sites are catalytically inactive. To confirm that the acidity at $pK_a \leq -3.0$ is responsible in bringing about the depolymerisation of paraldehyde all the catalysts were poisoned by dicinnamal acetone ($pK_a = -3.0$) and were used in the reaction. No depolymerisation took place in presence of these poisoned catalysts. It is thus observed that acid sites having an acid strength of $pK_a \leq -3.0$ alone are catalytically active for depolymerisation of paraldehyde. This observation agrees with the one made earlier by Tanabe and Takeshita⁹ and the present authors¹⁰ in the study of depolymerisation of paraldehyde. The present experimental evidence shows that the reaction of depolymerisation of paraldehyde is selective for solid acids and selectivity of catalysts plays an important role in every acid catalysed reaction.⁹

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